

A NOTE ON BROMINATION OF OXYMETHYLENE KETONES THROUGH THEIR COPPER SALTS

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Wislicenus and Ruthing (*Annalen*, 1912, 379, 260) brominated oxymethylene-desoxybenzoin in glacial acetic acid. Deshapande *et al.* (this *Journal*, 1946, 23, 43; 1949, 26, 55) effected the bromination of oxymethylene-cyclohexanone and oxymethylene-methyl-ethyl ketone in the same way. Brühl (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 2175, 2176) obtained bromo-oxymethylene-menthone and bromo-oxymethylene-camphor by adding bromine to the oxymethylene ketones, neutralised with caustic soda. Deshapande *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) obtained bromo-oxymethylene-acetophenone by the bromination of the sodium compound of oxymethylene-acetophenone in dry carbon tetrachloride.

We brominated oxymethylene-methyl-*n*-amyl ketone, oxymethylene-acetophenone and oxymethylene-camphor through their copper chelate compounds in an inert solvent. This method provides a better yield of the purer product, and the copper salt can be preserved easily. The copper salt method has been used in the preparation of α - γ -dibromoethyl acetoacetate from γ -bromoethyl acetoacetate. Although bromination of oxymethylene-methyl-*n*-amyl ketone has also been effected in ethereal solution, the copper salt method is found to yield better results.

Bromination of Oxymethylene-methyl-n-amyl Ketone.—Oxymethylene-methyl-*n*-amyl ketone (4 g.) (Bokadia and Deshapande, this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 383) was shaken with a saturated solution of aqueous copper acetate, forming a greenish blue copper salt, m.p. 130°. The copper salt was suspended in dry ether and to this bromine (2 *M*), suspended in dry ether, was added gradually with constant shaking in the cold. The copper bromide formed was removed by filtration. The filtrate on evaporation afforded a gummy mass, which on crystallisation from petroleum ether furnished a white solid, m.p. 69°, yield 1 g. It develops a violet colour with ferric chloride solution. (Found: Br, 36.2. $C_8H_{18}O_2Br$ requires Br, 36.9 per cent).

Bromo-oxymethylene-methyl-n-amyl Ketone from the Oxymethylene Ketone.—Oxymethylene-methyl-*n*-amyl ketone (2 g.) was dissolved in dry ether and to this bromine (1 *M*), suspended in dry ether, was added gradually in the cold. The solution on evaporation in cold gave the bromo derivative, m.p. 69°, after crystallisation. But the yield (0.2 g.) in this case was poor.

Bromo-oxymethylene-acetophenone.—The copper salt of oxymethylene-acetophenone (5 g.) was brominated, as described above, in dry CCl_4 . The solid product (yield 3 g.) on recrystallisation from acetic acid melted at 106° (cf. Deshapande *et al.*, *loc. cit.*).

Bromination of d-Oxymethylene-camphor.—The crude copper salt of *d*-oxymethylene-camphor (m.p. 160°, 2.5 g.) was brominated in the same way as before. Bromo-oxymethylene-camphor (yield 2.5 g.) after crystallisation from alcohol melted at 43° (cf. Aschan, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 2398; Brühl, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 746, 759; Fjader, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1933, II, 51).

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